

Positive Integration Teaching Method - Some Practical Issues (2010 - 2020)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 14, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 17, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Teaching Methods, Active Integration, Practical Practice, Self-Study</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12760537</p>	<p><i>The active harmonious teaching is one of the fundamental methods of innovating university teaching methods in Vietnam in the current context. Stemming from the research of practical experience in innovating teaching methods at Thu Dau Mot University and a number of universities in the South, the article analyzes the core issues of integrated teaching methods, such as: educational philosophy, active learning, self-learning capacity, practice activities - reality. With the above analysis, the article states that the innovation of university teaching methods towards positive integration contributes to improving the quality of training and the success of the university autonomy path.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching method is the common way and interaction between teachers and students in certain teaching conditions to achieve the goals of teaching; is the overall orientation of methodological action, in which there is a combination of many factors such as: teaching principles; Theoretical basis of teaching theory; teaching environment and conditions; specific orientation on the role of teachers and students when participating in the teaching process.

In essence, the connotation of university teaching methods always has interference, succession, inheritance, interleaving, sometimes nested. Therefore, there will be references to other methods in the presentation of active, harmonious teaching methods

1. The active harmonious teaching method

2.1. Educational philosophy

The philosophy of active and harmonious education is "learning-centered" education - from teacher-centered teaching, to student-centered teaching. This is a common trend in Vietnam and many countries around the world.

"Learning-centered approach" requires both the teacher and the learner to enhance activities in the class, clearly demonstrate their role in order to create an effective and control learning results, proactively improve themselves to get the best teaching effectiveness (Nguyen, 2019: 8-9).

Thu Dau Mot University, since its first years of establishment, has made efforts to seek and test many modern educational methods to improve the quality of training. In particular, since approaching the CDIO initiative and pursuing national and international accreditation standards, the University is more determined to use innovation in teaching methods as a lever that stimulates the spirit of teaching and active learning of the faculty and students of the school (Nguyen, 2019: 63). Through the practical experience of models to improve teaching capacity of faculty and students' learning capacity such as ISW, eLearning ... as well as the collaboration of international experts (most recently an IBM volunteer specialist), The School has clearly shaped the educational philosophy that the School pursues is a positive, inclusive education, based on the principle of "learning-centered principle".

2.2. Active learning

The harmonious - active teaching method aims at ensuring the training quality, helping students with actively learning and experiential learning, to meet the requirements of society.

The harmonious and active teaching method, the learner - the object of the teaching activity and the subject of the learning activity - is attracted to active learning activities organized by the teacher and guide, through which learners themselves discover unknown things, not passively absorb knowledge arranged by teachers. Placed in real life situations, learners can experience, directly observe, discuss, do experiments, and solve posed problems according to their way of thinking, both through individual work and teamwork, thereby gaining new knowledge, new skills, promoting creative potential (Uskov, Bakken, Howlett, & Jain, 2017). Depending on the goal of the specific subject, what level of knowledge or skill needs to be achieved, the teacher will organize appropriate activities to help students actively study to achieve those goals.

Thus, the learner is the center in the active - harmonious teaching method, the object of the "teaching" activity, and at the same time the subject of the "learning" activity. Teaching in this way, the teacher not only simply imparts knowledge but also guides actions.

The harmonious - active teaching method must have promoted the activeness, initiative and creativity of learners. In this method, special attention is paid to the initiative, positivity, towards activating and activating the learners' cognitive activities, which means focusing on promoting the activeness of learners, not focusing on promoting the teacher's initiative, however, in order to teach using active method, teachers have to put more effort than passive teaching method (McCune & Entwistle, 2011).

In the harmonious - active teaching method, it should first be clearly demonstrated through the design of detailed subject outline. We should not assume that a detailed subject outline is a list of knowledge contents to be learned, but should understand that it is the plan of activities to help learners achieve the goals (A. R. Marchand, 2019a). Therefore, the harmonious, active teaching method should be clearly shown in the outline. Teachers must create learning opportunities through diverse activities that stimulate students to discover, apply, analyze, and evaluate ideas rather than one-way communication. Students will have the opportunity to ask questions, raise problems to revolve around concepts or ideas, then progress to solving problems. Learners will feel always aware of their learning process, what they are learning and how to learn. This is also an advanced way for learners to build learning motivation and form lifelong learning habits (Marchand, 2019a: 142-144).

With this approach, students almost achieve the desired results and they feel satisfied with the education they receive when they learn actively, actively participate in a variety of learning activities. Active and active learning helps students get a deep approach in the learning process. The in-depth approach means that students intentionally explore concepts, rather than merely reproducing information in exams (Edward et al., 2007). The rate of learners' absorption of knowledge increases when applying multi-senses to learning activities, used in practice and especially if it is re-taught (passed on) to others. The harmonious - active teaching method is to organize diversified and rich learning activities to increase the ability to acquire knowledge (Biggs, 2003).

2.3. Improve self-study ability

Active, harmonious teaching methods - actively focus on training self-study methods for students, a measure to improve teaching efficiency. In modern society with information explosion, teachers themselves cannot gather enough information and cannot stuff more and more students into the minds of students. The role of the teacher is no longer the "communicator", but must teach students self-study methods from the first subjects of the program. Among the learning methods, the core is self-study (Trinh, 2008). And the classroom is a communication environment between teachers - students, students - students, creating a cooperative relationship between individuals on the way to acquire knowledge. Through discussion and debate in the collective, each individual's opinion is revealed, affirmed or denied, through which learners raise themselves to a new level. This is in accordance with the practical environment later when students graduate and go to work, forcing everyone to learn for a lifetime, combining individual learning and collaborative learning.

The role of the teacher in the active-harmonious teaching method is being an instructor, organizing activities; playing the role of designing, organizing, and guiding independent activities or small groups so that students can dominate learning content by themselves, actively achieving the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required by program (Lipmanowics & McCandless, 2014). In the class, the main students are active, the lecturers are the instructors. But before going to class, lecturers must invest a lot of time to design the lessons to achieve the required output standards; select teaching methods and assessment methods suitable to the objectives and content of the lecture. During the teaching process, outside of class time, teachers also have to keep track of students' self-study activities, help when necessary, exchange discussions and make suggestions for learners on the right track. Active - harmonious teaching methods that require teachers in active teaching and learning require a lot of time and effort compared to passive teaching and learning to take lessons with the role is an evocative, catalyst, motivator, advisor, and referee in students' exciting exploration and debate activities.

Positive, harmonious teaching requires combining faculty assessment with student self-assessment. According to traditional methods, in the past, teachers had monopoly on student assessment, but in the positive and harmonious teaching method, the instructor must guide students to develop self-assessment skills to self-regulate their learning. Concerning this, teachers need to create favorable conditions for students to participate in mutual assessment. Proper self-esteem and timely adjustment are essential competencies for success in life that the university must equip students. One thing to note in the assessment is that it must be process-based, avoid focusing on the assessment at the end of the semester and diversify the assessment activities to give learners a chance to show their progress learning process (Marchand, 2019b: 203-211).

2.4. Increase practice practice - reality

Practice - reality is the concretization of the learning method goes hand in hand with practice has great significance in learning knowledge from reality; and initial work environment experience. This is an opportunity for students to have a clear picture of the future work position, the knowledge and skills that need to be retrofitted to meet the job requirements (Constantinou, Tsivitanidou & Rybska, 2018) (Watts, 2014).

For the intern admitting units - reality, in the short term, the internship reception helps the units add staff during the season as well as save the cost of using labor. In addition, the trainees are also a plentiful and qualified source of human resources, the unit can recruit internships into full-time staff without wasting time or additional training costs. In the long term, from receiving internships, units can find out the insufficiency and gaps between their needs and the quality of the school's training, thereby giving suggestions to help the school to adjust the training program more effectively, employers also have the opportunity to recruit suitable staff with higher quality. In addition, the internship program - practically helps to develop the relationship between students - schools and businesses, towards a deeper and broader connection, balancing input - output in the future of human resources (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2016).

Most of the public universities have the Graduate Internship module which is implemented in the 8th semester, accounting for 5 credits in the curriculum framework - history pedagogy, literature pedagogy. Depending on the regulations of each school, the structure of graduation is different, students have to choose either to do a thesis or write an internship report and study additional subjects to replace the dissertation or to do the whole two: writing practice report while doing thesis. Although the structure of the modules is different, but for the internship program, the schools stipulate that students contact the internship by themselves, while the Faculty and the school only support and introduce students who cannot contact. The content of the program is also quite similar, usually includes 3 phases: (i) General practice: overview of the internship unit; (ii) Intensive practice (for writing in-depth reports or doing graduation thesis): students learn in-depth about the selected topic; and (iii) Completion of internship report, graduation thesis.

Every year, a very large number of students have to self-contact with local units and businesses to practice. This implementation allows students to increase initiative and learn from practice, and is also a major factor to reduce the pressure on the Faculty, the school to contact and organize internships - reality (Pham & Nguyen, 2020). Some disciplines organize practical internships for students by taking 10-20-day trans-Vietnamese tours (Duy Tan University, 2018). However, the reality of internship implementation in schools also appears many shortcomings and practical results are not as expected, most schools have not paid attention to the issue of career orientation and skills training for students have not properly assessed the importance of the practical internship process.

Therefore, in order for the practice - reality to be effective, creating conditions for students to apply the theory, the knowledge has been learned into practice and the practice of professional skills and professional skills on a practical basis, thereby reinforcing knowledge and training skills and attitudes of students before graduation. Practice-reality activities of students must (Hanoi National University, 2020):

- Ensure to meet the output standards of knowledge and skills of the training program through experiential activities to help students get acquainted with the actual working environment.
- Promote students' autonomy and creativity, improve their employability while being a student and after graduation.
- Create opportunities for students to show their own abilities; have the ability to analyze and evaluate for a specific job; improve self-confidence, personal orientation, develop action plans for themselves, establish social relationships, have skills to handle arising situations.
- Help students get acquainted with different institutions and organizations of society, recognize social relationships in a work unit and have appropriate behavior, intercultural communication, practice carefully living and working in a competitive multicultural environment.
- Implement innovation in teaching, linking training between schools and businesses to enhance students' employability and adaptability.

Instructors to guide students to practice are assigned by the Dean / Director of the Training Program and need to satisfy the following conditions: have taught the subject knowledge modules for 3 years or more or have a master's degree or a doctorate in the right discipline. Lecturers, managers, graduate students, and instructors of the internship institution who are invited to co-instruct and evaluate the intern must meet this requirement.

Each lecturer tutors no more than 15 students in each internship, not more than 8 students in each semester.

Content that instructors guide students to practice:

- Examine the plan and do the assessment according to the Student Practice Diary;
- Guide students to collect data, documents, write general internship reports, select and register research topics;
- Examine the subject's name, preliminary outline and detailed outline of the subject;
- Edit real draft thematic practice;
- Check and approve the report's objectivity and honesty (it is recommended to use specialized software to check the repeatability / copy of the report).

Along with the process of studying in the lecture hall, the time of internship is really meaningful, the role is not small with the growth of students and career opportunities in the future.

In universities in general, students' internships usually take place at the end of year 3 or 4. This is when students choose and look for a place to practice, get acquainted with the real working environment after a long period of studying in lecture-room. When understanding how to take advantage of the internship period, students will have many opportunities to develop in the future.

Practice – reality is an opportunity for students to improve and perfect their soft skills. Because some universities have programs or subjects of soft skills, but still heavily in theory. Soft skills are only improved and gradually perfected in real life and in the working environment.

Through communication activities, behavior, presentations or group work while working in the office, students will gradually improve and practice, perfect their soft skills. Undeniably, in addition to the learning results, soft skills will be an equally important factor to help students have job opportunities and development in the future.

Internship is an opportunity for students to directly apply the knowledge in the school to the practical working environment. An office environment will be very different when sitting in a lecture hall to gain knowledge. Although in the position of a trainee, students will have to complete the assigned work in accordance with their qualifications and requirements to complete as an employee. This is also an opportunity for students to get acquainted with a new environment, new people and a new job. Relationship is expanded, when self-capacity is shown through position and good dedication will definitely pay off. Many students are kept working at the company, becoming full-time employees after finishing that internship. And when you have had the time to practice during the internship, the students, and now the official staff, will develop more smoothly, and the chances of advancement will also increase.

Conclusion

Active-harmonious teaching is one of the fundamental methods of innovating university teaching methods in the current context, derived from the practice of teaching how to learn and learning to learn for life, by provoking curiosity, by creating the attraction of knowledge and by self-learning examples, teachers strive to create learning passion for students; promote the activeness of learners according to the motto "Student-centered teaching"; "Interactive teaching", "Teaching technology"...

Active - harmonious teaching method is to promote interaction between teachers and students, in order to achieve the goals of teaching. That process requires teachers, schools and students to apply well the harmonious-active teaching method, increase practice activities.

Today, with Vietnam in the transition to a knowledge economy, the role of universities to contribute to economic growth has become more important than ever. Applying the harmonious-active teaching method requires teachers to be a trainer, an instructor, a referee to advise students and a researcher, explore and discover new things in them, expand the relationships with the actual work, life to update themselves and learners, to meet social needs.

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